

MODERN METHODS IN EDUCATION: ONLINE LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract. Today, at a time when great changes are taking place around us, the demand for learning foreign languages is increasing in our country. As a result, the study of English language is very deep. With the initiatives of our President, English is widely taught in all educational fields. The use of technologies in the process of learning English is giving effective results. Especially in the current age of technology, the distance learning system is developing and many learners are also preferring to study in this way. Using this, this article discusses the great importance given to foreign languages in our country and the modern technologies necessary for learning them.

Keywords: online learning, foreign language, game, innovative technology, methods, technological tools, distance learning.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ: ОНЛАЙН-ОБУЧЕНИЕ ЯЗЫКАМ

Аннотация. Сегодня, когда вокруг нас происходят большие перемены, в нашей стране возрастает спрос на изучение иностранных языков. В результате изучение английского языка проходит очень глубоко. По инициативе нашего Президента английский язык широко преподается во всех областях образования. Использование технологий в процессе изучения английского языка дает эффективные результаты. Особенно в нынешний век технологий система дистанционного обучения развивается, и многие учащиеся также предпочитают учиться таким образом. Используя это, в данной статье рассматривается большое значение, придаваемое иностранным языкам в нашей стране, и современные технологии, необходимые для их изучения.

Ключевые слова: онлайн-обучение, иностранный язык, игра, инновационная технология, методы, технологические средства, дистанционное обучение.

Introduction

Modern methods and technologies in education is the efficient use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It also envisages increasing the quality and efficiency of education through importing modern innovative technologies in the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in the learning of the foreign language. The role of modern analysis in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological means is hand to help the foreign language is helpful in the study language (reading, writing, listening and speaking). In the educational process, in the use of modern technologies, both students are also an important factor in good knowledge and use of information and communication technologies. The teaching of a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective ways.

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending overwide and physical force. In short term, it requires supplying specific theoretical knowledge to students, creating their practice and skills in which are in certain activities, as well as, control of students, assessing the knowledge, skills and

skills they are occupied by them that the teacher is higher pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process.

Today, a number of developed countries have accumulated a lot of experience in this regard, and the methods that form the basis of this experience are being used under the name of modern methods. Below we will talk about the nature and use of online language learning, one of the modern methods used in educational practice. Distance learning is becoming a tradition in educational institutions. It is known that distance learning allows students to demonstrate their abilities, learn while concentrating, be able to learn a language whenever and wherever they want, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.

In the article, we will discuss in detail the features of distance learning English compared to regular classes, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of distance learning English courses.

Disadvantages: Social interaction.

Students who choose distance learning English instead of regular group classes do not have constant opportunities for social interaction with their peers or classmates (except in conversation groups). It may not be useful for speaking practice and new acquaintances.

Technical problems.

Often, whether English lessons are held today or not depends on the speed of the Internet connection or the provider. Because of this, sometimes online students cannot do homework when they should.

Motivation.

Some students need motivation to enter the classroom class. Learning a language under comfortable household will sometimes remain small, which often leads to ignorance and negligence.

Advantages: A wide selection of programs and courses.

It should be noted that in addition to the true purpose of learning English, an important and sometimes decisive factor is locating these lessons. Sometimes it restricts the choice of reading. The distance learning process, on the contrary, it gives a chance not worry about where you are. When you choose English in distance learning, you only focus on interesting sides of the language and you do not waste time.

Career growth and hobbies.

Online learning allows you to be flexible. That is, you do not need to leave your own interests and hobbies, worrying about your own interests and hobbies to spend one or two hours of city to spend a time and arrive at the time. The remote English course is a great opportunity to conduct a teacher and not adapt to other people in the group.

Environmental.

Distance English courses mean a special learning environment that best suits your needs such as a private room, educational institution, coffee shop or local gym.

Read with your own pace.

You can finish the online course faster than a traditional training program. This can be especially useful for students accustomed to perform the assignment plan earlier. You do not have to repeat what you don't miss joint classes and others do not understand 100 times.

Writing and communication skills.

With the learning of online learning, all your interactions are done in the online environment. In other words, the idea about people depends primarily on the ability to express

their views through a letter. Based on this, by the passage of time you will be able to form your point of view lexical diverse and grammatically.

As you can see, the advantages of learning English are more than flaws. In general, we can say that the teaching of online and offline includes three common components: teacher, student and textbook. Only the form of material will change, while the result will remain unchanged.

Opportunities for remote review of English are:

The most common method is that this zoom is in a distance in English with a teacher. Depending on the wishes and interests of the student online, online schools will choose an ideal teacher for the student, with which the educational process will not only be effective but also interesting. Here the student can choose English for itself a teacher who speaks English.

Furthermore, access to the popularity and use of online courses allows people to carry their own businesses without any convenient place, as well as working or studying.

Conclusion: *In short, as a result of using modern methods in learning a foreign language online, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods make the student eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded and mature person, in the future, we future teachers can make our contribution by developing ways to effectively use modern technologies.*

REFERENCES

1. Bakhrom, K., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). THEORETICAL BASICS FOR ENGLISH TEACHING. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 157-158.
2. G. Djumambetova, B. Khabibullaeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). DIFFERENCES AND SIMILARITIES OF PROVERBS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 106-107.
3. Jumaeva Mukarrama, Azimov Jasurbek, & Saidov Kamoliddin. (2022). TEACHING LISTENING SKILLS IN ENGLISH. *Academica Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(06), 252–255.
4. Jumayeva, M. (2022). ISLOM MA'RIFATINING TA'LIM-TARBIYA SIVILIZATSIYASIGA TA'SIRI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(8), 41–44.
5. Jumayeva, Mukarrama Bekzodovna (2022). OLIY TA'LIMDA INNOVATION USUL VA VOSITALAR. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2 (Special Issue 20), 214-226.
6. M. Jumayeva (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. Science and innovation, 1 (B7), 711-714.
7. M. Jumayeva (2022). EFFECTIVE CREATIVE WAY OF ERKIN VAHIDOV. TRANSLATOR, POET, HERO OF UZBEKISTAN.. Science and innovation, 1 (B5), 404-409. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7059373

8. M. Jumayeva (2022). UYG'ONISH DAVRI ALLOMALARINING PEDAGOGIKA VA TA'LIMTARBIYAGA O'ZGACHA YONDASHUV ASOSIDAGI QARASHLARI TAHLILI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 26-29. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6990805
9. M. Jumayeva, & M. Jumayeva (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF FEATURE FILMS IN INCREASING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B7), 581-583. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7257719
10. M. Jumayeva, & M. Mahmudova (2022). INGLIZ TILIDA TALAFFUZNI SHAKLLANTIRISH TAMOYILLARI. *Science and innovation*, 1 (B5), 263-265. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7027100
11. M. Kholdorova, N. Fayziyeva, F. Rixsittilayeva. "Use of assistants in foreign language teaching". Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, 2005.
12. M. R. Otaboeva. The use of modern innovative technologies in foreign language teaching and its operation. *Young uchenyy*. - 2017. p. 36-37.
13. Maxmudjonov Ibroximjon, & Jumayeva Mukarrama. (2022). HOZIRGI KUN YOSHLARINI IJTIMOYIY MUNOSABATLARGA KIRISHISHIDA CHET TILLARINI O'RGATILISHI VA UNING AHAMIYATI. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(5), 178–182.
14. Mukarrama Bekzodovna Jumayeva (2021). INTERACTIVE METHODS USED IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS. *Scientific progress*, 2 (4), 881-885.
15. Q. Xatamova, M.N.Mirzayeva. "Interactive methods used in english lessons" (methodical manual), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages.
16. Turdieva Umidaxon, & Jumaeva Mukarrama. (2022). SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE AS A FACTOR IN DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM SPHERE. *Academic Research Journal*, 1(3), 16–23.
17. U.B. Bekmuratova. Address on "The use of innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012.
18. Umidjon, G., & Mukarrama, J. (2022). USED IN LESSON PROCESSES EFFICIENCY OF INTERACTIVE METHODS. TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 161-162.